

The role of motivation as a mediator of influence knowledge management on employee performance

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 1090–1100

Publication history: Received on 10 December 2022; revised on 24 January 2023; accepted on 26 January 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0126>

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine and analyze The Role of Motivation as a Mediator of Influence Knowledge Management on the Employee Performance. This type of research is explanatory research. This research was conducted using a survey method to 104 civil servants in Kendari City. The data analysis used is Structural Equation Models analysis. Collecting data using a questionnaire. The analytical tools used are descriptive analysis and SEM analysis with SmartPLS. The results showed that knowledge management directly had a positive and significant effect on employee performance, work involvement directly had a positive and significant effect on employee performance, motivation directly had a positive and significant effect on employee performance, knowledge management directly had a positive and significant effect on motivation, direct work involvement has a positive and significant effect on motivation, the effect of knowledge management on employee performance mediated by motivation has a positive and significant effect and the effect of work involvement on employee performance mediated by motivation has a positive but not significant effect.

Keywords: Motivation; Knowledge Management; Employee Performance; Civil servant; SEM

1. Introduction

The importance of HR performance in creating a high-performing organization, to support the implementation of organizational programs to achieve organizational goals. Performance is the result of individual or group work within an organization in order to achieve organizational goals and is used as the basis for evaluating whether or not organizational goals have been achieved. Performance is formally defined as the value of various employee behaviors that contribute, either positively or negatively, to achieving organizational goals (11). Performance is the achievement of employees in the organization and is a benchmark for organizational success. Indicators for measuring performance are work quality, work quantity, toughness, and attitude (22). Performance is important because the sustainability of the organization is very dependent on the performance of the individuals in the organization.

The importance of performance needs to be considered by organizational leaders, especially the factors that can affect individual performance in the organization. There are many factors that influence performance including motivation, knowledge management, and work involvement ((50);(43)).

Motivation has the effect of increasing performance both intrinsically and extrinsically, a person will be motivated to do the job seriously or work hard so that his performance increases ((85);(77)). Several previous studies have shown that motivation influences employee performance. ((25); (100); (70); (75); (89); (37)), however, work motivation can also have a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance ((40); (18)).

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Knowledge management plays a very important role in improving employee performance ((42); (62); (98)), however knowledge management does not always have a positive and significant effect on employee performance ((44); (73)).

Based on these studies indicate that knowledge management does not always improve employee performance. This shows that the results of previous research have not been consistent, therefore it is necessary to know that the causes of knowledge management do not affect performance. The search for the results of previous research above also shows that motivation is an important factor that has a role in improving performance and knowledge management is one of the driving factors that can increase motivation, therefore researchers add motivation as a mediating variable in completing the research model ((54); (4); (92); (93)).

2. Literature and hypothesis review

2.1. The Influence of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance

Knowledge Management is a systematic coordination within an organization that manages human resources, technology, processes and organizational structures in order to increase value through reuse and innovation (14). Therefore knowledge management will be successful if there is systematic coordination between employees in the overall organizational structure. Research conducted by (42) shows that knowledge management indirectly affects employee performance. This is supported by research by (62) and (98) who found that knowledge management has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis 1: Knowledge Management has a positive and significant impact on Employee Performance

2.2. The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance

Motivation means a condition that encourages or causes someone to carry out an act or activity that takes place consciously (28). Motivation is a condition or energy that drives employees who are directed or directed to achieve the company's organizational goals. The positive mental attitude of employees towards work situations strengthens their work motivation to achieve maximum performance. Research conducted by (70) shows work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is supported by research by (25), (75) who found that motivation plays an important role and has a positive effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis 2: Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance

2.3. The Effect of Knowledge Management on Employee Motivation

Knowledge Management is positively related to motivation for organizational success, especially in manufacturing companies (27). Research conducted by (19) shows that knowledge management influences motivation. This is supported by research conducted by (98) showing that knowledge management has a positive effect on employee motivation.

Hypothesis 3: Knowledge Management has a positive and significant impact on Employee Motivation

2.4. The Role of Motivation in Mediating the Effect of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance

Knowledge Management is an effort to plan, coordinate, manage and control resources to achieve goals efficiently and effectively. Research conducted by (4) shows that knowledge management has a significant effect on employee performance through work motivation. This is supported by research by (54) who found that the need for motivational conduction in transferring knowledge affects employee performance.

Hypothesis 4: Motivation plays a positive and significant role in mediating the effect of knowledge management on employee performance

3. Research methods

This research approach is verification and explanation (explanatory research) which is intended to provide an explanation of the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing (Cooper & Schindler, 2003). The underlying reason for using explanatory research is because the purpose of this study is to explain and examine the role of motivation in mediating the effect of Knowledge Management and work involvement on employee performance. This

research was conducted using a survey method to 104 civil servants in Kendari City. The data analysis used is Structural Equation Models analysis.

4. Results

There are two stages of testing or evaluation, namely testing the measurement model (Outer Model) which aims to test the validity and reliability of each indicator on each variable, and testing the structural model (Inner Model) which aims to test the research hypotheses proposed in this study. Testing using the smart PLS program, the results of loading on the full model of this study are as follows:

4.1. Outer Model Testing

Based on the results of outer loading on the path analysis in this study, it can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1 Construct Validity and Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Ket.
Knowledge Management (X1)	0.918	0.922	0.932	Reliabel
Work Engagement (X2)	0.950	0.950	0.958	Reliabel
Motivation (Y1)	0.924	0.928	0.936	Reliabel
Employee Performance (Y2)	0.921	0.925	0.935	Reliabel

Table 2 Result for Outer Loading

Item/Indicator	Knowledge Management	Motivation	Performance	AVE
X1.1.1	0.768			0.606
X1.1.2	0.864			
X1.1.3	0.738			
Knowledge creation	0.790			
X1.2.1	0.769			
X1.2.2	0.830			
X1.2.3	0.759			
Use of Knowledge	0.786			
X1.3.1	0.756			
X1.3.2	0.810			
X1.3.3	0.701			
Sharing knowledge	0.756			
Y1.1.1		0.729		
Y1.1.2		0.723		
Y1.1.3		0.694		
Y1.1.4		0.795		
Y1.1.5		0.850		
<i>Motivation Factor</i>		0.758		
Y1.2.1		0,663		

Y1.2.2		0.835		
Y1.2.3		0.737		
Y1.2.4		0.744		
Y1.2.5		0.789		
Y1.2.6		0.738		
<i>Hygiene Factor</i>		0.751		
Y2.1.1			0.773	0.619
Y2.1.2			0.899	
Y2.1.3			0.686	
Y2.1.4			0.891	
Employee Work Goals:			0.812	
Y2.2.1			0.705	
Y2.2.2			0.677	
Y2.2.3			0.852	
Y2.2.4			0.750	
Y2.2.5			0.812	
Employee Work Behavior			0.759	

Based on the results of the outer loading above, it can be seen that all indicators have a coefficient value of r above 0.5 and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is above 0.5 so that the convergent validity test requirements have been met. Therefore all questionnaire items can be used for subsequent data analysis.

4.2. Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

4.2.1. R-Square

Changes in the R-Square value can be used to explain the effect of certain exogenous latent variables (X) on endogenous latent variables (Y) whether they have a substantive effect or not. The R-Square value of 0.70 indicates the model is at a strong level, 0.50 indicates the model is at a moderate level, and 0.25 indicates the model is at a weak level (Ghozali, 2012). The R-Square value in the construct is as follows:

Table 3 R-Square

Konstruk	R-Square
Motivasi	0.866
Kinerja	0.810

Based on table 3, the R-Square value of the influence of the Knowledge Management construct (X1) on Motivation (Y1) is 0.866. Meanwhile, the influence of the Knowledge Management (X1) and Motivation (Y1) constructs on Performance (Y2) is 0.810. This value is at a strong level (above 0.70) which means that all exogenous variables consisting of knowledge management and motivation have an effect on performance of 81%. Therefore it can be concluded that the performance variable is able to be explained by these two variables by 81%, while the remaining 19% is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

4.2.2. Hypothesis testing

After running the PLS-SEM algorithm, an estimate of the structural model relationship is obtained, namely the path coefficient value which can be seen in the original sample value which represents the hypothesized relationship between constructs. The value of the path coefficient or path coefficient is presented in table 4 as follows:

Table 4 Path Coefficient (P-Value)

Konstruk Jalur	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Ket.
Knowledge Management → Performance	0.302	0.297	0.110	2.752	0.006	+/Sig.
Motivation → Performance	0.323	0.318	0.113	2.853	0.005	+/Sig.
Knowledge Management → Motivation	0.772	0.774	0.077	9.981	0.000	+/Sig.

Based on the results of data processing in table 4 above, it can be seen in testing each hypothesis that has been proposed, namely:

- The Effect of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance

The first hypothesis put forward in this study is "knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance". Table 4 shows the original sample estimate value between the influence of knowledge management on employee performance of 0.302 and a positive value and a p value of 0.006 (p value <0.05). This value indicates that knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. So that the first hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. The effect of knowledge management on employee performance in this study can be explained that the better the knowledge management of employees in the Regional Government Organization (OPD) of the Regional Government of South Konawe Regency, the more their performance will improve.

- The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance

The third hypothesis proposed in this study is "motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance". Table 4 shows the original sample estimate value between the influence of motivation on employee performance of 0.323 and a positive value and a p value of 0.005 (p value <0.05). This value indicates that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. So that the third hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. The role of motivation on employee performance in this study can be explained that the better the motivation of employees in the Regional Government Organization (OPD) of the Regional Government of South Konawe Regency, the more their performance will improve.

- The Effect of Knowledge Management on Motivation

The fourth hypothesis proposed in this study is "knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on motivation". Table 4 shows the original sample estimate value between the influence of knowledge management on motivation of 0.772 and a positive value and a p value of 0.000 (p value <0.05). This value indicates that knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on motivation. So that the fourth hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. The effect of knowledge management on motivation in this study can be explained that the better knowledge management carried out by employees at the Regional Government Organization (OPD) of the Regional Government of South Konawe Regency will further increase their motivation.

Based on the opinion of (29), it is possible to test the mediating effect between the variables in this study by looking at the values in the Specific Indirect Effect table and the p-value, where according to (29) if the p value of the indirect effect is less than 0.05, it can be said that the intervening variable in the study has a significant influence as a mediator between variables.

Table 5 Specific Indirect Effects

Mediation Path	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	ket .
Knowledge Management → Motivation → Performance	0.249	0.247	0.093	2.688	0.007	+/S ig.

The Effect of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance Through Motivation

The sixth hypothesis proposed in this study is "knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through motivation". Table 5. shows the original sample estimate value of the effect of knowledge management on employee performance through motivation of 0.249 and a positive value. The statistical t value is 2.591 and the p value is 0.007 (p value <0.05). This value indicates that knowledge management has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through motivation. So that the fourth hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. The effect of knowledge management on employee performance through motivation in this study can be explained that the better knowledge management is carried out, the better performance will be through increased motivation.

5. Discussion

5.1. The Influence of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing indicate that the better the knowledge management in the form of knowledge creation, use of knowledge and knowledge sharing, the performance will increase both in terms of achieving performance targets consisting of quality, quantity, time and cost efficiency, as well as the achievement of work behavior in the form of service orientation. which is getting better, commitment is getting better, work initiative is getting better, cooperation is getting better and leadership skills are getting better.

The results of this study indicate that the better employees are at finding additional information on the internet to facilitate their work, the more often employees obtain additional information from meeting results and the more often employees attend webinars to increase their knowledge, the higher the ability to create knowledge carried out by employees to improve the quality of their work , the more capable the employee is in completing all the tasks and responsibilities assigned to him and is able to complete the work in a timely and cost-effective manner.

The results of this study prove that knowledge management that is carried out properly by employees will have an impact on improving their performance, both through increasing knowledge creation, increasing knowledge use and knowledge sharing. The results of this study are not in line with the research findings of (73) which states that knowledge management, even though it has been done well, is not able to significantly improve employee performance. The results of the research by (44) also found the same thing as (73), where the findings of (44) succeeded in revealing that although knowledge management has an influence, it is not significant in improving employee performance.

5.2. The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

The results of hypothesis testing show that employees who always try to complete office work well, always want to be appreciated for their work by superiors, are always challenged with office tasks, have responsibilities while working make the achievement of work goals and work behavior higher, as well as the better the employees are able delegate authority to subordinates, employees always conduct briefings before work, have good relations with subordinates, receive salaries on time and receive health insurance, the achievement of work goals and employee work behavior is higher.

The results of this study found that motivation is an important factor that can improve performance, this finding is in line with the findings of research conducted by (70) which stated that high motivation significantly increases performance. The results of research by (89) which state that motivation is an encouragement that exists in employees to achieve something that is a goal will try to improve the achievements of their work well, this is in line with the findings of this study which found that motivation can significantly improve performance.

5.3. The Influence of Knowledge Management on Motivation

The results of this study indicate that knowledge management carried out well by employees can significantly increase motivation factors and hygiene factors. These findings explain that the creation of knowledge, use of knowledge and knowledge sharing by employees can increase motivation. The findings of this study found that the motivation factor is the highest indicator perceived by respondents as a reflection of employee motivation, this shows that employee motivation is reflected in the motivation factor which can be increased by performing good knowledge management such as creating knowledge, using knowledge and sharing knowledge.

The research results of (19) revealed that if knowledge management is implemented properly, employees will be motivated to be more motivated in carrying out their work properly. The results of this study reinforce the findings of (19) by stating that knowledge management which consists of creating knowledge, using knowledge, and sharing knowledge can significantly increase motivation. The same thing was also expressed by (98) who stated that employee motivation would increase if employees were able to create knowledge, use knowledge and share knowledge. However, different results were found by (13) which revealed that although knowledge management has been carried out well, the fact is that good knowledge management has nothing to do with employee motivation.

5.4. The Influence of Knowledge Management on Employee Performance Through Motivation

The results of testing the hypothesis indicate that the better the knowledge management carried out by employees, the better their performance will be because good knowledge management will encourage increased employee motivation to achieve better work results. The findings of this study prove that the better knowledge management is carried out by employees such as increasing the creation of knowledge in facilitating their work, using the knowledge acquired to carry out their work, and sharing the knowledge possessed to facilitate their work significantly increases employee motivation to work even better and in the end achievement of work goals and work behavior of employees is getting better.

The results of this study are in line with the facts on the ground which show that employees at the Regional Government Organization (OPD) of the Regional Government of Konawe Selatan Regency are employees with a high level of education, namely bachelor and master graduates. This is a fact that employees at the Regional Government Organization (OPD) of the Regional Government South Konawe Regency are people who are trying to increase their knowledge to create knowledge that makes their work easier.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank all elements involved who helped in the data collection procedure.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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